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Research Article

**ROLE OF NURSING ASSOCIATION IN EMPOWERMENT OF
NURSING IN GUJRANWALA DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL
SIALKOT**¹ FouziaAmanullah, ² Najma Shaheen, ³ Ghulam Fizza¹Charge Nurse, Collage Of Nursing Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College Sialkot.
Email id: ff000459@gmail.com²Assistant Nursing Instructor, College of Nursing Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College
Sialkot,

Email id hammadhasni13@gmail.com

³Assistant Nursing Instructor, College of nursing Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College
Sialkot, fizzabajwa63@gmail.com**Abstract:****Introduction:** When nurses are empowered they participate actively and play a productive role in their working environment and society.**Objective:** "Role of nursing association in empowering of nursing in Gujranwala DHQ Teaching Hospital Sialkot.**Materials & methods:** It was descriptive, quantitative, cross-sectional study in nature in which 20 nurses included. Self-administered questionnaires were used to collect the data from the participants.**Results:** There were 20 nurses appeared in the study with an age range of 20 years to 50 years old. 90% respondents reported their job was providing challenging work whereas only 45% participants said that their current job was providing chance to gain new skills and knowledge and 80% revealed new tasks were also assigned to them and it was the contribution of nursing association to improve their working conditions at the workplace. 70% participants were strongly agree that their current environment empowered them to accomplish their jobs effectively and efficiently and 30% participants were agreed.**Conclusion:** Majority of the participants revealed an effective role of nursing association in improving their workplace environment. Consequently, role of nursing association found to be effective in terms of providing challenging working environment, motivating them, providing opportunities to take innovative ideas at the workplace, improving their working conditions, compensation, fringe benefits.**Keywords:** Nursing association, motivation, empowerment, working conditions, workplace, competencies etc.**Corresponding author:****FouziaAmanullah,**

Charge nurse,

Collage Of Nursing Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot.,

Email id: ff000459@gmail.com,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Empowerment have various meaning crosswise. Workplace empowerment is the chance of a person to have access to recourses, information and support needed to attain organizational aims in performing their duties. Empowerment is very important for nurses as it enhances self-management, job satisfaction and improves excellence in quality patient care. Employees work as a partner in decision making providing high quality care and achieving high agency goal. (Lu, Zhao, & While, 2019)

Empowerment in nurses is vital for both the health care system and society as a whole. For the health care system empowered nurse's results in more job satisfaction, increased nurse retention, and ultimately enhancing their commitment towards their profession. For society empowered nurses to become a source of motivation for others and provide more compassionate care through community coordination and mobilization.(Gholami, Saki, & Hossein Pour, 2019)

In the organizational context two different theoretical orientations of empowerment are differentiated: (1) structural empowerment (SE), and (2) psychological empowerment. Structural empowerment include work place condition that give confidence to increase employee performance and provide access to information, resources support and opportunity to learn Access to resources involves the nurses' ability to access supplies, resources and materials required to reach organizational goal(García Sierra & Fernández Castro, 2018)

Access to information is important in structural empowerments that include material goods and funds for employee to carry out these activities. Access to opportunity is another way to grow within organization and increase knowledge and skills. Opportunity can advance in the organization when nurses have access to learning and development. Nurses that have access to these working conditions are empowered to accomplish their work. (Shapira Lishchinsky & Benoliel, 2019).

Nurses get access to support by receiving feedback and guidance from subordinates, peers and superiors. Such support leads to autonomous decision-making and innovation. Nurses that have access to these working conditions are empowered to accomplish their work.(Mansour & Mattukoyya, 2018)

Structural empowerment differs from psychological empowerment which refers to an employee's

psychological response to empowering work conditions. Psychological empowerment is defined as the employee's experience of intrinsic motivation based on four cognitions: meaning, competence, impact and self-determination, reflecting an employee in relation to his or her work role. Within the context of nursing, meaning refers to the fit between nurses' values, beliefs, behaviours and their occupational require(Cummings et al., 2018).

When nurses are empowered they participate actively and play a productive role in their working environment and society as well. Empowered nurses take initiative through pattern of professional growth, being a change agent in the work environment and through commitment of the highest standard of patient care (Wei et al., 2018). Implication for nursing management managers must know the role of empowerment in work promotion and effectiveness among new nurse.(Cummings et al., 2018).

Empowerment of nurses also increase job satisfaction decrease burnout and contribute to increase organizational commitment as well as create positive impacts on patient safety and quality of care in health services. All things considered, the current effect of an empowerment and preventing turnover at the same time as investing in human capital result in a positive social change and unequivocally change the society for the better.(Aloisio et al., 2018)

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Empowering nurses is essential for improving work outcomes, and understanding the role of structural and psychological empowerment in supporting nurses' work motivation and occupational mental health are essential to stimulate nurses' productivity and preserve their mental health.

The concept of empowerment was first described for 30 years back. A five-year study took place in a large organization and discovering the relationship between empowerment and organizational structure. Kanter's theory suggests that a leader's competency is mainly influenced by an organization's behavior in the form of providing formal and informal power. A structurally empowered working environment allows its employs to access to resources, information, and support.

Heiyoung Kang 1 and Kihye Han 2, conducted cross-sectional correlational study.The study aimed to evaluate the moderating effects of structural empowerment and resilience in the relationship between workplace bullying and nursing work outcomes. Data were collected from 435 nurses and

nurse managers working at a tertiary hospital in Seoul, South Korea.

The moderating effects were examined using stepwise hierarchical multiple regression models. The bootstrapping method was utilized to verify the magnitude and significance of the moderating effects. (K. Heiyoung & H. Kihye. (2021). Moderating Effect Of Structural Empowerment and Resilience in the Relationship between Nurses Workplace Bullying and Work outcomes: A Cross-Sectional Study).

Heiyoung et al described that Structural empowerment showed a moderating effect in the relationship between workplace bullying and nursing work outcomes: for the conditional values above the average level of structural empowerment, workplace bullying was significantly associated with nursing work outcomes, while work outcomes were low regardless of workplace bullying for the conditional values less than average.

However, resilience had no moderating effect. To improve work outcomes, bullying must be reduced and structural empowerment and resilience increase. (K. Heiyoung & H. Kihye. (2021). Moderating Effect Of Structural Empowerment and Resilience in the Relationship between Nurses Workplace Bullying and Work outcomes: A Cross-Sectional Study)

Sheila Boamah conducted a cross-sectional survey with a randomly selected sample of 378 registered nurses working in direct patient care in acute care hospitals across Ontario, Canada. Structural equation modeling was used to test the hypothesized model. Results: The model had an acceptable fit, and all paths were significant. Transformational leadership was significantly associated with decreased adverse patient outcomes through structural empowerment and staff nurse clinical leadership (Sheila Boamah, 2017. Linking Nurses' Clinical Leadership to Patient Care Quality: The Role of Transformational Leadership And Workplace Empowerment)

Khadra Mohammed et al (2020) conducted a study the Background: Talented nurses create differential value and make contributions to the hospital; talent management has been advocated as an important scheme to empower those nurses. The study aimed to measure the effect of a talent management training program on nurses' empowerment. A quasi-experimental one-group pre-posttest research design was used. Subjects and Setting: The sample consisted of 145 nurses who were invited to participate in the study. The study was conducted at Fayoum University Hospitals. Researchers used two tools for data collection namely; Talent management and empowerment questionnaires.

Liaqat. Met. al explained in their studies that the health care system is a diverse environment that is continuously changing and requires effective decision-making skills among nurses. Nurses should be skillful in clinical decision making to quickly analyze the situation and make an effective plan of care that ineffectively meets the patient's needs. Due to its diversity nurses often meet such situations that demand critical thinking and decision-making skills.

Empowering work environments enable nurses to practice according to their professional standards and use their expertise, skills, and knowledge to provide safe quality care for patients (Boamah, Read, & Laschinger, 2016; Laschinger & Leiter, 2006). In such an environment, nurses have support to develop collegial partnerships, which promote their continued professional growth that fosters their use of clinical leadership behaviors at the bedside (Patrick, Laschinger, Wong, & Finegan, 2011).

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Study design:

The study was descriptive (Quantitative) in nature & cross-sectional study design (observational design) was adopted because the data was collected from many different individuals at a single point.

3.2. Study setting:

The study was conducted at Gujranwala DHQ teaching hospital sialkot.

3.3. Duration of study:

The study completed in 6 weeks (from 15-05-2022 to 30-06-2022).

3.4. Study Population:

Nurses of Gujranwala DHQ teaching hospital sialkot.

3.5. Sample size & sampling

In the population of 21 nurses following sample was drawn for the study by using listed below formulae:

$N =$ Population = 21; $n =$ Sample Size; $E =$ Margin error = 0.05

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(E)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{21}{1 + 21(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{21}{1 + 21(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{21}{1 + 0.0525}$$

$$n = \frac{21}{1.0525}$$

$$n = 19.95$$

Thus, a more suitable sample of n= 20 considered for the study.

3.6. Sampling Technique:

Convenient sampling technique.

3.7. Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Nurses age range 20-50 years old included in the study.
- Both single and married nurses included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Nurses less than 20 years old age excluded from the study.
- Nurses older 50 years excluded from the study.

3.8. Data collection method

Self-administered questionnaire were used to collect the data from the study participants.

3.9. Ethical consideration

This study was approved by the ethical review committee of the institution and performed in accordance with the principles of Committee. To ensure their voluntary participation, inform consent

was obtained from all the participants. All participants had autonomy to withdraw their consent at any time during the stipulated period of the study.

3.10. Data Analysis

The descriptive data statistically investigated using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 20. Results inferred through frequencies and percentages to check the accuracy of data. Data was represented in graphs, tables and MS excel used to check the accuracy of data.

RESULTS:

Current study undertaken at College of Nursing Khawaja Muhammad Safdar, Medical College, Sialkot regarding role of nursing association in empowerment of nursing in which 20 participants recruited between age 20 to 50 years old out of which 20% belonged to an age group of (20-25) years; 15% participants having age group (26-30) years; 20% having age group (31-35) years; 10% belonged to (36-40) years; 5% had (41-45) years and remaining 30% respondents were between 46 to 50 years old as depicted in the table no. 4.1. and figure no. 4.1.

Table 4.1. Demographic data of the participants

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-25 years	4	20.00
26-30 years	3	15.00
31-35 years	4	20.00
36-40 years	2	10.00
41-45 years	1	5.00
46-50 years	6	30.00
Total	20	100.00
Marital status		
Single	7	35.00
Married	13	65.00
Total	20	100.00
Educational status		
Matric, BS Generic	3	15.00
Matric, FA/FSC, Specialized in CCU	5	25.00
Matric, FSC, Post RN	12	60.00
Total	20	100.00

Figure 4.1. Age of the participants

Figure 4.2. Marital status of the participants

Figure 4.3. Educational status of the participants

In the sample of 20 participants, 35% single and 65% married respondents appeared in the research work. As per educational status of study participants, there were 15% having Matric, BS Generic qualification, 25% having Matric, FA/FSC, specialized in CCU and rest of the 60% got Post RN as shown in the table no. 4.1. and figure no. 4.2. to 4.3.

Table 4.2. Role of nursing association in nursing empowerment (n=20)

Questions	Options	None (f) %	Some (f) %	A lot (f) %
How much of each kind of opportunity do you have in your present job?	Challenging work	2 (10%)	3 (15%)	15 (75%)
	The chance to gain new skills and knowledge on the job	3 (15%)	6 (30%)	11 (55%)
	Task	4 (20%)	7 (35%)	9 (45%)
How much access to information do you have in your present job?	The current state of the hospital	0 (0%)	5 (25%)	15 (75%)
	The values of top management	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	18 (90%)
	The goals of top management	0 (0%)	6 (30%)	14 (70%)
How much access to support do you have in your present job?	Specific information about things you do well	0 (0%)	7 (35%)	13 (65%)
	Specific comments about things you could improve	0 (0%)	4 (20%)	16 (80%)

	Helpful hints or problem solving advice	0 (0%)	1 (5%)	19 (95%)
How much access to resources do you have in present job?	Time available to do necessary paper work	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	17 (85%)
	Time available to accomplish job requirements	1 (5%)	6 (30%)	13 (65%)
	Acquiring temporary help when needed	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	20 (100%)
In my work setting /job?	The rewards for innovation on the job are	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	20 (100%)
	The amount of flexibility in my job is	2 (10%)	6 (30%)	12 (60%)
	The amount of visibility of my work –related activities within the institution is	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	18 (90%)
How much opportunity do you have for these activities in your present job?	Collaborating on patient care with physician	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	17 (85%)
	Being sought out by peers for help with problem	0 (0%)	6 (30%)	14 (70%)
	Being sought out by managers for help with problem	0 (0%)	8 (40%)	12 (60%)
	Seeking out ideas from professionals other than physicians e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, dieticians	0 (0%)	7 (35%)	13 (65%)
Questions	Options	Strongly agree(f) %	Agree (f) %	Strongly disagree (f) %
How much opportunity do you have for these activities in your present job?	Overall, my current environment empowers me to accomplish my work in effective manner	14 (70%)	6 (30%)	0 (0%)
	Overall, I consider my workplace to be an empowering my environment	2 (10%)	18 (90%)	0 (0%)

It was cross-sectional research and quantitative in nature in which 20 participants included to assess the role of nursing association in nursing empowerment. 90% respondents reported their job was providing challenging work whereas only 45% participants said that their current job was providing chance to gain new skills and knowledge and 80%

revealed new tasks were also assigned to them and it was the contribution of nursing association to improve their working conditions at the workplace as recorded in the table no. 4.2. As 20 participants appeared in the study and 25% reported they had some access to the information regarding current state of the hospital while 75% replied a lot. Even 30% participants reported they had little knowledge

about the management goals whereas 70% responded they were well aware about the goals of the top management. Out of 20 participants 35% said they had some support regarding specific information of the things they did well and rest of the 65% said they had a lot support regarding their performance as indicated in the table no. 4.2.

85% participants reported they had a lot time to complete paper work and other denied. Even 65% respondents revealed they had enough time to complete the job requirement and remaining said some time. 100% participants said they acquired rewards for the innovation in the job while 30% participants said they encounter some flexibility in the current job. In the sample of 20 respondents, 35% disclosed they had some opportunities to seek ideas from other professionals too and remaining 65% told they got sufficient opportunities to find out better ideas from other professionals other than doctors.

Overall, role of nursing association was found to be positive in improving the working conditions of the nurses as 70% participants were strongly agree that their current environment empowered them to accomplish their jobs effectively and efficiently and 30% participants were agreed. Majority of the participants revealed that their current job empowering them and rewarding them for doing innovations at the workplace recorded in the table no. 4.2.

CONCLUSION:

Majority of the participants revealed an effective role of nursing association in improving their workplace environment. Consequently, role of nursing association found to be effective in terms of providing challenging working environment, motivating them, providing opportunities to take innovative ideas at the workplace, improving their working conditions, compensation, fringe benefits.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ◆ Nursing association should enhance nursing competencies for high quality patient care.
- ◆ No doubt, nursing association empowering nurses but this empower should be positive e.g., win-win situation in which the rights of both employee and employer must be protected.
- ◆ Nursing association should retain most knowledge-intensive and experienced nurses to meet the organizational goals of the organization.
- ◆ Employees empowerment does matter and having good impact on overall efficiency of the organization and for this purpose that

employees must have strong critical thinking, interpersonal skills and clinical skills to improve patient care in healthcare sector. So, nursing association not only focus on improving the working conditions but also improve capabilities of nursing staffs.

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